

4-Quinazolones. Part IX.

Synthesis of 3-Benzenesulphonyl-2-thioquinazolin-4(3H)-one and its Transformation into Some Thiazolido (3,2-a) quinazolones

Buddhadeo Singh and Late D. N. Chaudhury

Benzenesulphonylisothiocyanate (I) reacted with anthranilic acid to give N-benzenesulphonyl-N'-(*o*-carboxyphenyl) thiourea (IV) which cyclised to 3-benzenesulphonyl-2-thioquinazolin-4(3H)-one (V). It was converted into 2-phenacyl/*p*-bromophenacylthio-3-benzenesulphonylquinazolin-4(3H)-one (VIa, b) and 2-carboethoxymethyl-3-benzenesulphonyl-quinazolin-4(3H)-one (VIc). These were reduced with potassium borohydride and cyclised to thiazolido(3,2-a)quinazolones : IXa, b and X respectively.

Although a number of 2-thioquinazolin-4(3H)-ones with a variety of substituents at the 3-position are known¹, 3-benzenesulphonyl-2-thioquinazolin-4(3H)-one (V) is hitherto unreported in the literature. McFarland and Houser² recently described a preparative method for benzenesulphonylisothiocyanate (I) and showed that it reacted with glycine to produce N-(benzenesulphonyl)-N'-(acetic acid) thiourea (II) which was subsequently cyclised into the five-membered-ring compound (III). Since the reagent I is now readily available, it seemed possible to build the six-membered-heterocyclic ring of the thioquinazolone V by replacing glycine with anthranilic acid in the reaction sequence. This was realised in the present investigation. Thus, the amino group of anthranilic acid added to I affording N-(benzenesulphonyl)-N'-(*o*-carboxyphenyl)-thiourea (IV) which, with PPA or preferably in the presence of concentrated sulphuric acid, cyclised to the thioquinazolone V. Its structure is supported by elemental analysis, i.r.-spectrum and chemical reactivity. When treated with phenacyl bromide, *p*-bromophenacyl bromide and ethyl bromoacetate, the methanolic solution of sodium salt of (V), obtained by the interaction with sodium methoxide, readily formed 2-phenacyl-, 2-*p*-bromophenacyl and 2-carboethoxymethyl derivatives : VIa,b,c respectively.

As an extension of our method³ for the preparation of thiazolido(3,2-a)quinazolones, the keto sulphides VIa,b were treated with potassium borohydride which reduced simultaneously the cyclic C = N and C = O bonds and the products, 3-benzenesulphonyl-1,2-dihydro-2-(α -hydroxyphenethyl)thioquinazolin-4(3H)-one (VIIa) and 3-benzenesulphonyl-1,2-dihydro-2-(α -hydroxy-*p*-bromophenethyl)thioquinazolin-4(3H)-one (VIIb), were smoothly cyclodehydrated with a trace of *p*-toluenesulphonic acid to furnish respectively 4-benzenesulphonyl-1-phenylthiazolido(3,2-a)quinazolin-5(4H)-one and 4-benzenesulphonyl-1-*p*-bromophenylthiazolido(3,2-a)quinazolin-5(4H)-one, (IXa,b).

1. Fused Pyrimidines edited by D. J. Brown, Part I., Quinazolines, W. L. F. Armarego, Interscience Publishers, 1967, pp. 306, 309.
2. J. W. McFarland and R. Houser, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1968, **33**, 340.
3. B. D. Singh and (Late) D. N. Chaudhury, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1970, **47**, 759.

The ester VIc is insoluble in aqueous sodium bicarbonate but readily dissolves in sodium hydroxide solution at the room temperature, thereby indicating the ease with which the carboethoxy group is hydrolysed; acidification of the alkaline solution precipitated the acid VIId. In accordance with our previous observation³, treatment of an alkaline solution of the ester VIc or the acid VIId with an excess of potassium borohydride at the room temperature followed by acidification resulted in the separation of 4-benzenesulphonylthiazolido(3,2-a)quinazolin-1,5(4H)-dione (X). It is obvious that the precursor to cyclic lactam formation must be the intermediate reduction product VIII, cyclisation of which proceeded only in acidic solution. In the case of VIc, the reduction of the cyclic imine bond is accompanied with the hydrolysis of the ester group caused by the alkaline reaction medium. The tricyclic lactam X is readily soluble in aqueous sodium hydroxide and reprecipitated on acidification. Thus under basic condition, the thiazolidone ring is easily opened as has been observed by us in similar instances³.

EXPERIMENTAL

Benzenesulphonylisothiocyanate (I): It was prepared according to the published procedure². It was distilled under reduced pressure (oil bath temperature, 130–140°) and the distillate immediately solidified, m.p. 113° without crystallisation. (lit². b.p. 103–105°/0.5 mm.; on long standing the liquid solidified, m.p. 118–120° after crystallisation from CHCl₃).

N-(Benzenesulphonyl)-*N'*-(*o*-carboxyphenyl)thiourea (IV): To a solution of benzenesulphonylisothiocyanate (2.46 g.) in Na-dried hot benzene (20 ml.) was added anthranilic acid (1.7 g.) dissolved in hot Na-dried benzene (10 ml.), and the mixture refluxed on water bath when a yellow crystalline precipitate separated out from the clear solution within 5 mins. The mixture was heated for 6 hr. and allowed to cool to room temperature. The precipitate was collected, washed with hot benzene and crystallised from ethyl acetate to

afford IV as yellowish needles (3.2 g.), m.p. 156°. Found : C, 50.25; H, 3.40; N, 8.56. $C_{14}H_{12}N_2O_4S_2$ requires : C, 50.00; H, 3.57; N, 8.33%.

IR(KBr) 1675 ($> C = O$), 1635 cm^{-1} ($> NH$).

It is readily soluble in aqueous $NaHCO_3$, Na_2CO_3 and $NaOH$ and is reprecipitated on acidification.

3-Benzenesulphonyl-2-thioquinazolin-4(3H)one (V): *Method* (a) : The thiourea IV (5 g.) was mixed with conc. H_2SO_4 (20 ml.) and allowed to stand at room temperature overnight. The clear solution was poured into crushed ice and excess conc. NH_4OH (d, 0.88) added when a yellowish precipitate separated. It was allowed to stand in ice-chest for 4 hrs., the solid filtered, washed with water and crystallised from ethanol to furnish V as pale yellow needles (3 g.), m.p. 327°. IR (KBr) 1650 ($> C = O$), 1640 ($> NH$), 1180 cm^{-1} ($-SO_2-N <$). (Found : C, 52.65; H, 3.35; N, 8.50. $C_{14}H_{10}N_2O_3S_2$ requires : C, 52.83; H, 3.14; N, 8.80%.

Method (b) : A mixture of (IV) (1 g.) and commercial PPA (20 g.) was kept in an oil bath at 135–140° for 1 hr. and then poured into crushed ice with stirring. The solution was neutralised with conc. NH_4OH (d, 0.88), and the resulting precipitate was collected, washed and crystallised from ethanol to give V as pale yellow needles (0.6 g.), m.p. and mixed m.p. 327°.

The thioquinazalone V is soluble in aq. $NaOH$ and dil. mineral acids.

3-Benzenesulphonyl-2-phenacylthioquinazolin-4(3H)one (VIa) : V (3.18 g.) was dissolved in a methanolic solution of sodium methoxide (prepared from 20 ml. dry methanol and 0.23 g. Na) and the solution was cooled by keeping it in ice-cold water bath. To it was added phenacyl bromide (2 g.) dissolved in dry acetone (10 ml.) when colourless crystalline precipitate immediately separated. The cooled mixture was diluted with ice-water, the crystals filtered, washed with water, collected and recrystallised from glacial acetic acid to yield VIa as colourless needles (3.6 g.), m.p. 199°. IR (KBr) 1700 ($> C = O$), 1675 (tert. amide, $> C = O$), 1150 cm^{-1} ($-SO_2-N <$). Found : C, 60.72; H, 3.69; N, 6.61. $C_{22}H_{16}N_2O_4S_2$ requires : C, 60.55; H, 3.66; N, 6.42%.

3-Benzenesulphonyl-1,2-dihydro-2-(α -hydroxyphenethyl)-thioquinazolin-4(3H)-one (VIIa) : A solution of KBH_4 (0.5 g.) in water (5 ml.) was added dropwise to VIa (1 g.) dissolved in hot THF (10 ml.) when there was a vigorous reaction. After the addition was completed, the clear solution was allowed to stand overnight. THF was evaporated at the room temperature in air, cold water was added followed by dil. HCl to decompose excess borohydride. The colourless precipitate that separated out was filtered, washed with water and crystallised from methanol to afford VIIa as colourless felted needles (0.8 g.), m.p. $> 310^\circ$, with previous sintering and slight darkening at 152°. IR (KBr) 1675 ($> C = O$, tert. amide), 3350 (broad-OH), 1180 cm^{-1} ($-SO_2-N <$). Found : C, 60.30; H, 4.35; N, 6.54. $C_{22}H_{20}N_2O_4S_2$ requires : C, 60.00; H, 4.54; N, 6.36%.

4-Benzenesulphonyl-1-phenylthiazolido(3,2-a)quinazolin-5(4H)one (IXa) : A solution of VIIa (1 g.) in dry THF (15 ml.) was treated with a few crystals of *p*-toluenesulphonic acid and refluxed on water bath when within 5 min. colourless needles started depositing from

the clear solution. The reflux was continued for further 20 min., and after cooling the crystals were filtered off, washed with THF and crystallised from glacial acetic acid to give IXa as hexagonal colourless prisms (0.7 g.), m.p. $> 310^\circ$ with no sintering unlike the previous compound. IR (KBr) 1140 ($-\text{SO}_2-\text{N} <$), 1655 cm^{-1} (tert. amide, $> \text{C} = \text{O}$). Found: C, 62.80; H, 4.00; N, 6.84. $\text{C}_{22}\text{H}_{18}\text{N}_2\text{O}_3\text{S}_2$ requires: C, 62.55; H, 4.26; N, 6.63%.

3-Benzenesulphonyl-2-p-bromophenacylthioquinazolin-4(3H)-one (VIb): A cooled solution of V (3.18 g.) in a methanolic solution of sodium methoxide (prepared from 20 ml. dry MeOH and 0.23 g. Na) was treated with *p*-bromophenacyl bromide (2.8 g.) in dry acetone (10 ml.) and worked up as described for the preparation of VIa. The white solid isolated was crystallised from glacial acetic acid to furnish VIb as colourless needles (3.8 g.), m.p. $205\text{--}206^\circ$. Found: C, 51.00; H, 3.12; N, 5.64. $\text{C}_{22}\text{H}_{15}\text{N}_2\text{O}_4\text{S}_2\text{Br}$ requires: C, 51.26; H, 2.91, N, 5.43%.

*3-Benzenesulphonyl-1,2-dihydro-2-(α -hydroxy-*p*-bromophenethyl)-thioquinazolin-4(3H)-one* (VIIb): It was prepared according to the procedure adopted for VIIa by reducing a solution of VIb (1 g.) in THF (10 ml.) with KBH_4 (0.5 g.) in water (5 ml.). The solid isolated was crystallised from methanol to afford VIIb as colourless needles (1.5 g.), m.p. $> 310^\circ$ with previous sintering and slight darkening at 164° . Found: C, 50.63; H, 3.94; N, 5.52. $\text{C}_{22}\text{H}_{19}\text{N}_2\text{O}_4\text{S}_2\text{Br}$ requires: C, 50.86; H, 3.66; N, 5.39%.

*4-Benzenesulphonyl-1-p-bromophenylthiazolido(3,2-*a*)quinazolin-5(4H)-one* (IXb): It was prepared from a solution of VIIb (1 g.) in dry THF (15 ml.) and a few crystals of *p*-toluenesulphonic acid according to the procedure adopted for IXa. The solid obtained was crystallised from glacial acetic acid to furnish Xb as rods (0.8 g.), m.p. $> 310^\circ$. IR(KBr) 1140 ($-\text{SO}_2-\text{N} <$), 1655 cm^{-1} (tert. amide, $\text{C} = \text{O}$). Found: C, 52.60; H, 3.60; N, 5.75. $\text{C}_{22}\text{H}_{17}\text{N}_2\text{O}_3\text{S}_2\text{Br}$ requires: C, 52.69; H, 3.39; N, 5.58%.

3-Benzenesulphonyl-2-carboethoxymethylthioquinazolin-4(3H)-one (VIc): To an ice-cold solution of the thioquinazolone V (1.1 g.) dissolved in methanolic Na-methoxide (from 15 ml. dry methanol and 0.08 g. Na) was added with shaking ethyl bromoacetate (4 ml.) in dry methanol (2 ml.) when a white precipitate separated out. The mixture was kept cold in ice-water for an hour, diluted with cold water, the solid filtered off and washed with water. Crystallisation from methanol gave VIc as irregular plates (1.2 g.). It sintered at 188° with slight darkening which deepened on gradually raising the temperature until it completely melted at 295° to a dark liquid. IR(KBr) 1700 (ester, $> \text{C} = \text{O}$), 1640 (tert. amide, $> \text{C} = \text{O}$), 1156 cm^{-1} ($-\text{SO}_2-\text{N} <$). Found: C, 53.46; H, 3.96; N, 6.93. $\text{C}_{18}\text{H}_{16}\text{N}_2\text{O}_5\text{S}_2$ requires: C, 53.46; H, 3.96; N, 6.93%.

3-Benzenesulphonyl-2-carboxymethylthioquinazolin-4(3H)-one (VIId) The ester VIc (1 g.) was treated with aq. N-NaOH (10 ml.) when a clear solution was obtained. It was kept overnight at the room temperature, diluted with water (10 ml.) and filtered from traces of insoluble material. The filtrate was cooled and acidified with 6*N* HCl and the white precipitate that separated was collected, washed with ice-cold water and crystallised from glacial acetic acid to give the acid VIId as colourless needles (0.7 g.); it melts at 225° to a dark liquid with previous sintering at 195° . Found: C, 51.20; H, 3.42; N, 7.66. $\text{C}_{16}\text{H}_{12}\text{N}_2\text{O}_5\text{S}_2$ requires: C, 51.06; H, 3.19; N, 7.44%.

4-Benzenesulphonylthiazolido(3,2-a)quinazoline-1,5(4H)-dione (X) : Method (a) : A solution of the ester VIc (1 g.) in THF (10 ml.) was treated with KBH_4 (0.5 g.), dissolved in water (5 ml.) and the homogeneous solution was kept overnight at the room temperature. After evaporating THF at the room temperature the solution was diluted with ice-cold water and filtered from traces of insoluble material. The filtrate was cooled and acidified with 6*N* HCl when white precipitate separated out. It was filtered, washed with water and crystallised from glacial acetic acid to give X as clusters of prisms (0.6 g.), melting at 305° to a dark liquid. IR(KBr) 1640 (tert. amide, $> \text{C} = \text{O}$), 1720 (lactam, $> \text{C} = \text{O}$), 1156 cm^{-1} ($-\text{SO}_2-\text{N} <$). Found : C, 53.27; H, 3.46; N, 7.90. $\text{C}_{16}\text{H}_{12}\text{N}_2\text{O}_4\text{S}_2$ requires : C, 53.33; H, 3.33; N, 7.77%.

It is insoluble in aq. NaHCO_3 , but readily dissolves in aq. NaOH and reprecipitated on acidification.

Method (b) : The acid VIId (1 g.) dissolved in aq. NaOH (10 ml.) was treated with KBH_4 (0.5 g.) in portions and set aside overnight at the room temperature. It was diluted with water (10 ml.) filtered from traces of impurities, cooled and acidified with 6*N* HCl. The white solid that separated was, washed and crystallised from glacial acetic acid to furnish X (0.6 g.), m.p. and mixed m.p. 305°.

Chemical Laboratory,
Bihar University,
L. S. College,
Muzaffarpur.

Received October 31, 1970